

Candidate Pattern	Game	☰	Universal Level	Tr	Variant suggestion	Diary entry
Non-Playable Time	Metroid Dread	Safety		<u>Loading Screen</u>		"During the loading screen, the game displays tips and my latest updates."
Make Your Path	Celeste	Autonomy		<u>Sidequest Choices</u>		"At various points, there are optional challenges, such as collecting collectibles, which are not mandatory to advance in the game. The player can choose whether or not to collect them, which reinforces this feeling of freedom."
Visual Support	Shadow of the Tomb Raider	Safety		<u>Ambiental guide</u>		"When the game guides by scene composition instead of overlay. Two ideas I would put in this direction, based on my experience, would be: a variant focused on attention guided by living elements or movement in the environment (like when something in the scenery catches my attention and kind of "takes" me to a point of progression)"
Visual Support	Shadow of the Tomb Raider	Safety		<u>Ambiental guide</u>		"A variant focused on markers that are materially consistent with the context (not just paint), for situations where the game needs to signal interactivity but wants to avoid the marker looking out of place in natural environments."
Adaptative Challenge	Teamfight Tactics	Competence		<u>Competitive Balance</u>		"My placement affected my sense of competence... there are always stronger comps than others."
Creative Suite		Competence		<u>Construction planning</u>		"Choose materials with more intention, and solve construction problems more efficiently, without improvising all the time."
Creative Suite	Minecraft	Competence		<u>Construction planning</u>		"I think something like a "construction planning" variant could be added to Creative Suite, which is when the game supports creation before execution, instead of throwing the player straight into the cost of error."
Creative Suite	Minecraft	Competence		<u>Construction planning</u>		"A variant focused on lightweight prototyping within the world itself (such as ghost blocks, drafts, scale previews, and material lists, so I can test variations without spending everything)"
Creative Suite	Minecraft	Competence		<u>Creation Preview</u>		"Could be added a variant focused on review and iteration tools that don't break the flow (more robust undo/redo, version comparison, saving project steps), so that experimentation is a natural part of the process and not a "risky" decision that I avoid for fear of wasting time and resources."
Progression	Minecraft	Competence		<u>Environment Evolution</u>		"I notice progress when I start to organize a space better."
Progression	Teamfight Tactics	Competence		<u>Fair Ranking</u>		"I also felt competent to win the match or achieve good positions in the ranking."
Adaptative Challenge	God of War: Ragnarok	Competence		<u>Item Adaptation</u>		"The game has a mechanic of buying a rare item that allows you, when you die, to immediately resurrect from the point where you died. You choose whether you want to use the item, your Companion uses the item on you in a cutscene, and combat resumes."
Companion	Teamfight Tactics	Relatedness		<u>Multiplayer Variants</u>		"Choose a different strategist for each match from among the strategists you have, also changing your relationship with other players through this cosmetic, since the game is multiplayer."
Visual Support	Celeste	Competence		<u>Reflective Messaging</u>		"The game communicates that deaths should not be seen as definitive failures, but as learning opportunities."
Visual Support	Shadow of the Tomb Raider	Safety		<u>Textual Incorporation</u>		"Could be added tutorials that arise linked to the element of action (e.g., the climbing tutorial is text in the world, which makes it much more dynamic; I look at the wall and the text is there teaching me)."